

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A503

15 December 1996

OMEGA

A503 15th December, 1996
 OMEGA
 South West Mediterranean

Start time	End time	Event	Height(s)	Hdg	Comments
093651					Take off from Valencia
101720	104624	P1	FL210 50ft	060	Profile P1
105113	112246	R1	300'	320	Run 1, 10 to 9
112431	113404	R2	300'	200	Run 2, 9 to 8
113457	115700	R3	300'	145	Run 3, 8 to 7
115840	120751	R4	300'	240	Run 4, 7 to 6
120840	123405	R5	300'	330	Run 5, 6 to 5
123545	124424	R6	300'	220	Run 6, 5 to 4
124538	130308	R7	300'	150	Run 7, 4 to 3
130613	132431	P2	50' FL150	290	Profile P2
132845	133343	R8.1	FL150	130	Run 8.1, ARIES calcs
133508	134007	R8.2	FL150	285	Run 8.2, ARIES calcs
134046	134205	01	FL150	020	Orbit 1, 50deg, r.w.down
134218	134319	02	FL150	080	Orbit 2, 60deg, r.w.down
134326	134440	03	FL150	120	Orbit 3, 55deg, r.w.down
135309	140110	R9	300'	030	Run 9
140202	140700	R10	300'	275	Run 10
140738	142136	R11	300'	210	Run 11
142224	142723	R12	300'	275	Run 12
142819	143818	R13	300'	030	Run 13
143926	144611	R14	300'	275	Run 14
144705	150207	R15	300'	210	Run 15
153049	153811	R16	300'	140	Run 16
154238	155240	R17	300'	345	Run 17
155657	160341	R18	300'	155	Run 18
160939	163511	P3	50' FL220	345	Profile P3
163511	165505	R19	300'	020	Run 19, ARIES calcs
170839					Land at Valencia

NERC ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

OMEGA

Date: 15/12/96

Flight No: A503

SORTIE OBJECTIVE: To provide a sea surface temperature map for RRS Discovery for SST intercomparison between ARIES, SAFIRE, Ship and Satellite measurements. Atmospheric and aerosol profiles will also be made.

LOCATION: Western Mediteranian.

Almeria Front

36°32'N	2°16'W	36°16'N	1°33'W
36°31'N	2°07'W	36°04'N	1°25'W
36°28'N	1°58'W	36°49'N	1°18'W
36°25'N	1°49'W	36°30'N	1°00'W
		36°30'N	0°05'W

RRS Discovery

Time (GMT)	Estimated Positions
13:30	36°14'N 1°46'W

WEATHER: Ideally clear sky conditions for satellite work, but otherwise sufficiently high cloud base for low level flying.

FLIGHT PATTERN:

Transit Outbound

- [1] Take-off. Transit from operational base at maximum altitude to position of IMG overpass (via Alicante, Magal).
- [2] Straight and level run (180 KIAS) at max altitude to turning point west of Hamra; straight and level run to northern end of stack. + 2 ORBITS (60°, 50°)

RRS Discovery

- [3] Establish a track A/B orientated perpendicular to the front and extending 15 nms either side of ships position. Complete two runs A-B, B-A at max altitude.
- [4] Commence profile from max altitude to 50 ft, along A-B interrupting profile and reversing as necessary. Two straight and level runs (along A-B) to be included at heights specified by aircraft scientist. Profile at 1000 ft per minute down to inversion, 500 ft per minute below.
- [5] Two straight and level runs A-B, B-A at 100 ft. Extend one run to allow for calibration (~3 min).
- [6] Straight and level run A-B at 300 ft.

SST Mapping

- [7] Transit at 300 ft to start point for SST mapping pattern.
- [8] Execute straight and level runs of SST mapping pattern.
- [9] Profile from 50 ft or minimum safe altitude to maximum altitude at 500 ft/min below inversion and 1000 ft/min above.
- [10] 15 minute straight and level run at maximum altitude.
- [11] Transit back to operational base as convenient.

FL 807

BAILÉN
BLN 116 2 Ch 109
N38°09'2"
W03°17'4"

RESTU
N37°53'3"
W01°34'2"

MADRID FIR
BARCELONA FIR

ALICANTE
ALT 113-8 CH 65
ALT 429
N38°18'1"
W00°41'2"

TCA FL245
VALENCIA
109

TCA FL245
PALMA
99

CTA FL460
BARCELONA
FL150

TOSGA
N37°27'8"
W02°18'3"

ROLAS
N37°25'0"
W02°31'2"

CTZ FL260
MURCIA

R77
FL300

MURCIA/SAN JAV
V3J 113-8 CH 77
TSJ CH 116 (T)

VALENCIA SECTOR
LEVANTE SECTOR

DT 20-1530
M-F
BY NOTAM

SURIB
N38°20'4"
E01°54'9"

CTA 75
GRANADA

ADRAS
N36°50'0"
W01°07'0"

ALMERIA
99

AMR
AMN
N36°50'
W02°75'

CTA FL460
MADRID
FL150

PLAN 98
D19
FL150-FL300

ALBORN
ALB 510

PLAN 97

MELILLA
MLL 117
CH 124
MLL 29
M 300
W 15

NADORTAOMA
NDR 414
N35°09'6"
W02°55'6"

CASABLANCA FIR
ALGIERS FIR

RAS AIGUILLES
02965

ORANES
ORA-N
N36°00'
W01°30'3"

MOSTAGANEM
MOS 112-2 Ch 99
MOS 334
N35°33'9"
E00°08'3"

DAHRA
N36°55'
E01°50'0"

M11
FL90

CHECH
CHE 397A1
N36°35'7"
E02°11'0"

UNLTD
0512

WAY POINT LIST.

T/O - Highlevel HAMRA

Profile down to 50' towards pt (10)

(10) 300ft SSTM

(10) - (9) - (8) - (7) - (6) - (5) - (4) - (3)

Profile 50' → FL150 overshoot (to FL25 in hoci)

ESTABLISH A & B and 2 levels. (A-B crosswind)

(ship stationary into wind)

Drop to 1st level A-B (10min)

Drop to 2nd level A-B (10min)

Drop to 100ft. A-B-A or B-A-B + cal.

up to 300ft A-B + cal.

START 300ft SSTM.

start creeping line ahead search
to map detail map of front.

↓ continue until out of time

----- time decision

50ft → needed profile

20 min run if clear

home.

NERC ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

OMEGA

Date: 15/12/96

Flight No: A503

Aircraft Scientist Debrief:

Large amounts of frontal clouds were encountered which resulted in difficult flying conditions at low level towards the end of the flight. These clouds were heavier than expected (bearing considerable amounts of rain) from local forecasts and satellite imagery. However a sea surface mapping pattern was flown which on a number of occasions clearly showed the temperature gradients associated with the Almerian front. Despite the difficult conditions several intercomparison runs were made past RRS Discovery at 100 and 300 feet.

Several orbits were made when clear skies were encountered at FL150 at the end of a profile. This was to characterize a new baffle in SAFIRE.

Maps of the sea surface temperature were sent to the Hotel, but the aircraft manager was unable to forward them to RRS Discovery.

Following the final profile to maximum altitude an area of Cirrus free sky above was identified. This facilitated zenith calibrations for SAFIRE and ARIES.

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A503

Date: 15.12.96

A/S Name: S. WILSON

A. KAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for ... ~~3~~... (MRF) ~~1~~... (STH) ~~1~~... RSI ~~1~~.....
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period ...! INDEF.....
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project C.M.F.
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? INDEF.....
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? ... MRF 14 [MFD, A503]
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye S. Wilson.

Project: OMEGA Date: 15/12/96

Flight No: A503 Page 1 of 1

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
9:42:38		TRANS	83	FL	177	39.18	-0.54	thin SC above. some small on over sea to port. Sun can be seen through cloud.	
9:53:45		TRAN	176	FL	194	38.53	-0.50	9800 cloud base thin cirrus above 10500 cloud top clear ahead.	
								sc below / clear above.	
9:59:40		TRAN	208	FL	137	38.15	-0.45	Broken sc below with lines of sc in visible Ci ahead.	
								Ci above not good for calcs. level off at FL 210. and proceed to Top of Provilla.	
10:13:45		TRAN	210	FL	197	37.08	-0.26	Ci above also on ahead Solid sc below.	
10:17:21		PIs	210	FL	55	36.88	-0.17	in cloud. band of blue sky visible ahead.	
								Ice crystal clouds - large ice crystals as distinct from yesterday group.	
10:24:35								1500 out of cloud. small on field out to starboard. with sc beyond	
10:27:17		PI	108	FL	49	37.31	0.61	thin Ci Above Ci across to starboard. Some small on calm sea & some haze.	
								10:30 sp 1013.8 WD 160 @ 5kts. Status from Discovery	
10:32:49		PI _{int}	60	FL	240 50	37.49	0.90	Ci above thin rale + 1/8 thicker Calm sea below.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Keage S. Wilson.

Project: OMEGA

Date: 15/12/96

Flight No: A503

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:34:57	18	R3	300	R	142	37.43	-0.66		
11:39						37.26	-0.50	Jump in SST 15.2 → 16°C	
11:46						36.91	-1.14	Surface streaking hazy - very visible change jump in SST.	
11:54:48	19					36.64	0.13	edge of frontal structure 11:51:30 penguin star oil tanker just to port	
11:57:00	20	R3e	300	R	149	36.54	0.21	overcast 8/8 SC with some cu visible.	
11:58:40	21	R4	300	R	241	36.48	0.13	two vortices visible of Portside not quite waterspouts but marking surface	
12:07:51	22	R4e	300	R		36.27	-0.33	dramatic drop in aerosol counts. 8/8 SC above some cu visible Seastate 3.	
12:09:40	23	R5	300	R	321	36.29	-0.38		
						36.63	-0.66	event 24 lots of surface marking reduced seastate (2)	
						36.90	-0.93	12:18 Aerosol print + with shiptrack!	
								event 25 surface peltchers.	
								Some oil slicks.	
12:34:05	26	R5e	300	R	320	37.34	-1.35	8/8 bright SC. some cu visible in distance.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: ~~S. Wilson~~ A. Kerge S. Wilson.

Project: OMEGA Date: 15/12/96
Flight No: A503 Page 2 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:33:42	10	P1 _{cut}	600	R	236	37.44	0.89	Some small cu fields ahead. clear above.	
10:41:50		P1	20	R	168	37.10	0.75	Passing through a small ^{short} band of small cu.	
10:46:26	11	P1 _e	50	R	175	36.94	0.78	cloud above calva print of Aerosol profile. 1014 sea state 2.	
10:51:11	12	R1	300	R	318	36.72	0.78	overcast cu's head.	
10:59:15		R1	300	R	323	37.07	0.48	Brighter clear skys ahead sc solid sc above.	
11:01:40						37.19	0.36	front visible on water	
	13*							event make 13 surface line with temp drop.	
11:12:37	13	R1	300	R	326	37.62	-0.03	sc highly structured multi layer clouds ahead. some sky gaps but much brighter.	
11:17:26		R1	300	R	326	37.82	-0.21	" sea state 2.	
11:22:45	14	R1 _e	300	R	316	38.02	-0.44	Broken sc with ci above some sunny.	
11:24:31	16	R2	300	R	196	37.46	-0.50	heavy overcast but 7/8 thin sc.	
11:34:04	17	R2 _e	300	R	196	37.47	-0.61	4/8 sc some banding visible	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: OMEGA Date: 15/12/96

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye S. Wilson.

Flight No: A503 Page 4 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:35:45	27	R6	300	R	217	37.28	-1.41	line of cu ahead.	
12:44:23	28	R6e	300	R	218	36.93	-1.76		
12:45:38	29	R7	300	R	141	36.87	-1.72	hazy, high ci & some cu flying away from squall line?	
						36.78	-1.67	event mark 30 front. ~1° Temperature Drop.	
								YANG MING LINE 12:52:02 passed just behind.	
13:02:30						36.18	-1.09	Rain on window.	
13:03:09	31	R7and	300	R	140	36.16	-1.08	Low cloud & rain water glassy surface.	
13:06:12	32	P2	50ft	R	283	36.16	-1.25	brighter ahead. 1/4 high cu visible. 1013 sea state 2.	
								36.09 N SW-3ms (2000) 285ms 001.61 W fm 270° 3800, 5000 ft	
13:24:30	36	P2e	150	FL	286	36.43	-2.40	clear above & 1/8 sc below.	
13:	37	R61	150	FL	125	36.25	-2.02	clear of ci above.	
133343	38	R81	150	FL		36.14	-1.76		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye S. Wilson.

Project: OMEGA Date: 15/12/96

Flight No: A503 Page 5 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
133508	39	R8.2	FL 150	P	278	36.08	-1.81	REMAINING UNDER CI FREE CONDITIONS	
134009	40	R8.2 ENDS	FL 150	P		36.12	-2.14		
134046	41	01	FL 150	P				50° ORBIT NO CI ABOVE	
		02	FL 150	P				60° ORBIT	
		03	FL 150	P				55° ORBIT	
134639			FL 123	P	75	36.10	-1.92	DESCEND FOR FINESCALE SSTM PATTERN	
135309	47	R9	300	R	27	36.27	-1.52	START OF SSTM. 8/8 SCU/CU ABOVE	
140110	48	END R9	300	R	29	36.66	-1.30		
140202	49	R10	300	R	269	36.67	-1.34	8/8 SCU ABOVE; HA 27.	
140700	50	R10 END	300	R		36.65	-1.65		
140738	51	R11	300	R	210	36.63	-1.67	REMAINING 8/8 CU/SCU ABOVE.	
141540	52		300	R	201	36.27	-1.91	OVERPASS OF FRONT.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye S. Wilson.

Project: OMEGA

Flight No: A563

Date: 15/12/96

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
142112	S3		300	R	202	36.03	-2.02	ON OTHER SIDE OF FRONT	
142136	S4	END R11	300	R		36.00	-2.09		
142224	S5	R12	300	R	262	36.00	-2.15	8/8 SC ABOVE	
142430			300	R	267	35.99	-2.29	PRECIPITATION	
142723	S6	R12 ENDS	300	R	268	35.99	-2.45	STILL SOME RAIN; 8/8 SC ABOVE	
142819	S7	R13	300	R	25	36.04	2.47		
143045			300	R	30	36.15	-2.61	CONTINUING I/TW. VISIB NOT GOOD!	
	S8		300	R	29			CROSSING FRONT AGAIN, SST (HEAVY DROPS)	
143615	S9		300	R	30	36.39	-2.24	TEMP DROPS AGAIN, AFTER RISE.	
143818	60	END R13	300	R	29	36.47	-2.17		
143926	61	R14	300	R	269	36.50	-2.20	8/8 cu / SCu	
	62		300	R	267			CROSSING FRONT ON CROSS RUN ⇒ cloud MOVE RUN NORTHWARDS	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye S. Wilson.

Project: OMEGA Date: 15/12/96
Flight No: A503 Page 7 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
144611	63	R14 END	300	R	319	36.58 -2.53	MOBE MOVED TO POSITION N. OF FRONT. STILL PPTN.		
144705	64	R15	300	R	204	36.57 -2.57			
1450	65		300	R	205	36.4 -2.64	START OF FRONT; STILL SOME PPTN. SST RISING		
145445	66		300	R	205	36.21 -2.27	SST LOW RISES AGAIN ? PEAK WITHIN FRONT		
145534			300	R	205	31.17 -2.80	PPT. INCREASES AGAIN: 8/8 SCU/cu. HEAT! VISIB NOT GOOD		
145840	67		300	R	205	36.02 -2.90	SST DROPS; PPTN INCREASING		
150207	68	R15 FWD	300	R	204	35.87 -3.00			
150803			300	R	57	35.95 -2.71	MODERATE HTW (TRANSIT TO SHIP)		
150952			300	R	57	35.98 -2.62	SEA STATE 3-4 VISIB NOT GOOD		
							SURFACE WIND 250 @ 4 KTS, VARIABLE		
151834							SEA STATE 2 LIGHT PPTN SEA STATE DECREASING, V. LIGHT WINDS		
152340			300	R	27	36.52 -2.16	SEA STATE T → 3,4		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kuyt S. Wilson.

Project: OMEGA

Date: 15/12/96

Flight No: A 503

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
153049	69	R16	100	R	138	36.43	-1.82	OVERPASS RRS DISCOVERY WIND WESTERLY, SKTS. PPTW STOPPED. VIS IMPROVING	
154811	70	END R16	100	R	154	36.13	-1.56	8/8 SCU (CU ABOVE) VISIB DECREASING AGAIN	
153918								20 REPORTS PPTW INCREASING	
154238	71	R17	300	R	340	36.03	-1.54		
155240	72	END R17	300	R	341	36.52	-1.78	VISIB FADING.	
155657	73	R18	100	R	153	36.53	-1.80	1010P SEASTATE 2, LIGHT PPTW ~ 34 MILES VISIB	
	74	END R18	100	R	161				
160939	75	P3	50	R	335	36.19	-1.68	1012mb SEASTATE 2 RATE OF ASCENT 500ft/min	
161930	76	P3	FL 6000	R	22	36.88	-1.47	RATE OF ASCENT → 1000ft/min PASSING THROUGH VARIOUS CLOUD LAYERS, CONT PPTW.	
1623			FL 103	P	22	36.91	-1.38	8/8 CLOUD ABOVE + BELOW!	
163511	77	END P3 START R19	FL 220	P	2	37.61	-0.87		
163650			FL 720	P	6			SLIGHT COURSE VARIATION	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye, S. Wilson

Project: OMEGA Date: 15/12/96

Flight No: AS03 Page 9 of 9

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
163940			FL 220	P	3	37.90	-0.78	VERY RARE PATCH OF Ci OVERHEAD	
164421			"	"	358	38.24	-0.73	7/8 ACU BELOW, LOWERS TO SCU?	
16448			"	"	358	38.50	-0.69	SMALL AMOUNT OF Ci (BAND) OVERHEAD	
165340			"	"	358	38.89	-0.62	CLOUD COMING BELOW.	
165505		R19 END	"	"	"	38.79	-0.60		

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A503

Date: ~~18.12.96~~

User: S. Wilson

Interactive by: M. Rule

15.12.96

Date: 13.1.97

Renav

Accepted Kalman Filter corrections

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = - 0.4904 E+1

b = + 0.3255 E-2

c = + 0.4295 E-6

LWC

ICTP ✓

Heimann / Barnes

No mods made

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A503 Date: 15.12.96

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
DF12	REF +	5	568	✓		Approx	0568
	REF -	7	2853	✓		Approx	2858
	AOSS	19	1800	Port F/S STBD O/S	TORQUE 3-7.5	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	00	Blk F/S Down O/S	TORQUE 3.0	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0	0	✓	As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	3876	1006 1/2	1005 + 0.2k	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3306	1004			
*	A/S	9	2	was 13 earlier	* 40	As ASI	0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	167	7			
	UP2S	82	157	2			
	UIRS	83	1929	-24			
	UP1Z	84	151	✓		Approx	0147
	UP2Z	85	145	✓		Approx	0149
	UIRZ	86	2033	-		Approx	2061
	UP1T	87	2749	+5	7.4	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2770	+4		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	2789	+3		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	126	SPIKING			
	LP2S	92					
4095	LIRS	93					
	LP1Z	94				Approx	0150
	LP2Z	95				Approx	0146
	LIRZ	96				Approx	2050
	LP1T	97				As IAT	
	LP2T	98				As IAT	
	LIRT	99				As IAT	
	J/W	42	997			As Indicated	0000
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	2453	9.3	0.1		
	HYCC	59	701	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	2164	8		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	608				
	DTF	10	2089				
	DTC	11	5	+7	✓		
	NDTF	23	1691			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5	+6	✓		
	INCT	48	2759				
	ECN	140				less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2475	✓		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72				0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100					
	O3P	106					
	O3RG	113				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0724	FL NO	1	Hex	503	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	072	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	443	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	5	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3147	1532 3832	3148	841	3146	3734 ✓	3146	124
	LATC	160	Dec	4094			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4094			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0726	TWCD	70	2347	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	932	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	77	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2239	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2238	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2075			0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2131			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1022	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	2043				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3509				
	EVIC	173	3968				
	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off/On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off/On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK Flight No: A503 Date: 15.12.96
for auto selection

Page...1...of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0942	REF +	5	566	✓			Approx 0588
	REF -	7	2853	✓			Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	1933	F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1221	F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	4095				As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	2818	8.7	✓		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	2995	286	908		
	A/S	9	1670	185	186 ✓		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	1083	332			
	UP2S	82	896	149			
	UIRS	83	1780	-54			
	UP1Z	84	155	✓			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	165	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	2072	✓			Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2854	+1	-2.0		As IAT
	UP2T	88	2849	✓			As IAT
	UIRT	89	2889	✓			As IAT
	LP1S	91	724	232			
	LP2S	92	460	.79			
	LIRS	93	0000				
	LP1Z	94	155	✓			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	170	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	2084	✓			Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2878	0	-4.4		As IAT
	LP2T	98	2852	+1			As IAT
	LIRT	99	2906	-2.			As IAT
	J/W	42	1562	0.3			As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	1201	-40.6	-43	climb thru FL140	
	HYCC	59	1109	c			696-901
	FDEW	138	1881				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	608				
	DTF	10	2721				
	DTC	11	4	-7	-7.8		
	NDTF	23	2159.				same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	4				
	INCT	48	2502				
	GCN	140					less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	2509				0000-4094
	TSAM	72	/				0840-1860 < min
	O3	100	/				
	O3P	106	/				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	/				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	503			Flight No.
	GMPH	2	Hex	095			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMPM	3	Hex	301			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	7			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
2439	1260 3855	2042	1243	2442	3756	2439	174 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	438	37		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4090	-1		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL180 ↗

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0954	TWCD	70	1322	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2545	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1291	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2511	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2226	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2494	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2250	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1015	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	3472				
	EV2V	171	3140				
	NPWR	172	2686				
	EVIC	173	4013				
	EV2C	174	3995				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre-~~In~~-Flight Check List

PTO →

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No:

Date:

Page...2...of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5				Approx 0568	
	REF -	7				Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19		F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18		F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37				As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8				As Altimeter	
	CABP	14					
	A/S	9				As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81					
	UP2S	82					
	UIRS	83					
	UP1Z	84				Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85				Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86				Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87				As IAT	
	UP2T	88				As IAT	
	UIRT	89				As IAT	
	LP1S	91					
	LP2S	92					
	LIRS	93					
	LP1Z	94				Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95				Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96				Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97				As IAT	
	LP2T	98				As IAT	
	LIRT	99				As IAT	
	J/W	42				As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58					
	HYCC	59				696-901	
	FDEW	138				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139					
	DTF	10					
	DTC	11					
	NDTF	23				same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24					
	INCT	48					
	CCN	140				less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70				0000-4094	
	TSAM	72				0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100					
	O3P	106				P ≈ (DRSU × 0.4) + 145mB	
	O3RG	113					

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex				Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex				Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex				Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex				Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
	LATC	160	Dec				Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec				Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 300ft

TAT = 13.6

occasional status light flash

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1445	TWCD	70	2755	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2580	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1396	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2509	✓	<i>occasional spike</i>	2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2260	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1903			0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1652			0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1013			0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095			4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 503.....

Date 15.12.96.....

Page 1..... of ... 4.....

Video Tape
No. A503 #1
Ends 1240
✓ FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	39° 29.35N	39° 29.36N
Long	000° 28.53W	000° 28.53W
Time	07:09:22	07:09:47
Status	✓	GC ALIGN.

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	CAMERA	Wind/Sea st.
063946		START	RECORDING							0/m/s ⁻¹
0855		INU to	NAVIGATE							
093651		TAKE OFF	FROM	VALENCIA.						
0945		Start Video	FFC						FFC	
		climb to Grand	MOA) alt.	FL210						
		Cirrus above so no	calls							
101720	8	FL210	START	PROFILE	P1 ↓			1000ft/min		271/29.
			—	060	180	-21.2	-20.7			
103219	9.	FL60	Interrupt	PROFILE	P1					
			—	055						
103342	10	FL60	Recommence	Profile	P1 ↓					
			—	240						
104624	11	50ft	END	PROFILE	P1					Sea state 2.
				1014	180					
105113	12.	300ft	START	RUN	1.		(10) → (9)			199/4
				1014	325	15.1	12.5			
105234.		Video to	DFC							
105833		Heimann	cal (2 → 15°C)						DFC	

Video Tape	
No.	A 503 #1
Ends	1240
✓ FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	37'19.38N	37'22.93W
Long	0'14.96E	000'11.66E
Time	11:06:53	110711
Status	✓	NAV.

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos reports	(y/n)

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS SST	TAT	DP	DI Htr	CAMERA FFC/DFC	Wind/ Sea st.
			END	RUN	1.					
112246	14.	300ft	1014.	320		14.5	9.8		FFC	
112248		Heinann	cal.	(12→18)					FFC	
			START	RUN	2.		(9)→(8)			
112431	16	300ft	1014	200	183	14.7	10.0		DFC	052/4.
			END	RUN	2					
113404	17	300ft	1014	200.						
			START	RUN	3		(8)→(7)			
113457	18	300ft	1014	145		14.1	10.0		DFC	005/3.
			END	RUN	3					
115700	19.	300ft	1014	145.	14.6				FFC	
1157		Heinann	cal	(12→18)						
			START	RUN	4.		(7)→(6)			
115840	21	300ft	1014	245	16.09				DFC	
			END	RUN	4.					
120751	22.	300ft	1014.	240	15.8	14.9	12.6		FFC	
			START	RUN	5		(6)→(5)			
120840	23.	300ft	1014	330				SS. 3.	DFC	
120850		Heinann	cal	(12→18)						
121709	24.	A/c Schmitt's EVM						SS 172.		
			END	RUN	5					
123405.	25	300ft	1014	330	14.94	15.2	9.5	SS	FFC	

1210 sst map.

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 503.....

Date 15.12.96.....

Page 2..... of 4.....

Video Tape		
No.	A503	# 2
Ends	1520	1535
☒ FFC / ☒ DFC / ☒ RFC		

	GPS	INU
Lat	36'49.13N	36'47.43N
Long	1'39.86W	1'38.40W
Time	12:47:10	12:47:44
Status	☒	NAV ☒

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS SST	TAT	DP	DI Htr	camera	Wind/ Sea st.
123410		Heimann	cal (12 → 18)							
			START	RUN	6		⑤ → ⑩			
123545	27	300ft	1014	220	15.23	15.1	11.3		DFC	030/4.
124140	/46	Stop video / Start video								
			END	RUN	6		raining		FFC	
124424	28	300ft	1014.	220	15.06	14.6	13.8		DFC	302/0
			START	RUN	7		④ → ③			
124538	29.	300ft	1014	145	14.93	14.6	13.1		DFC	
			END	RUN	7					
130308	31	300ft	1014	150					@ glassy sea	
									FFC	
		SSTMAP	— sent at		1310Z	(to hotel)				
130312		Heimann	cal. (12-18).							
			START	PROFILE P2	↗		keep 500ft/min			
130613	32.	50ft	1013	290	-		sea state = 2.		DFC.	
	⑬	38'15N	001 33.	— ship steaming to this pos. (RRS Discovery).						
131601	3	6500ft	increase r.o.a to 1000ft/min							
1322		Send SST	→ ship							
			END	PROFILE P2						
132431	36.	FL150	—	290						

Video Tape
 No. A503 #2
 Ends 1535
 ✓ FFC / DFC / RFC

	GPS	INU
Lat	36'13.25,	36 12.70
Long	1'55.65W	1'53.43W
Time	133137	13:32:01
Status	✓	NAV ✓

DRS recording to HORACE y/n
 HORACE recording to disc y/n
 SATCOM sending pos reports (y) n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			START	RUN	8.1		ARIES CALS		
132845	37	FL150	—	120	190	-9.2	-10.3		267/23
			END	RUN	8.1			FFC	
133343	38	FL150	—	130					
			START	RUN	8.2		ARIES CALS		
133508	39	FL150	—	290	186	-9.1	-11.2	FFC	277/21
			END	RUN	8.2				
134007	40	FL150	—	285					
134046	41	FL150	—	020		START ORBIT 1,		50° bank, r. wing down	
134205	42	FL150	—	020		END ORBIT 1			
134218	43	FL150	—	080		START ORBIT 2		60° r. wing down	
134319	44	FL150	—	080		END ORBIT 2			
134326	45	FL150	—	120		START ORBIT 3		55° r. w. down.	
134440	46	FL150	—	120		END ORBIT 3			
			START	RUN	9				
135309	47	300ft	1013	205 030	181	14.3	< 33.6 ← max wdl.		
135630		Heimann	col (12 → 18°)						
			END	RUN	9				
140110	48	300ft	1013	030				DFC	
			START	RUN	10				
140202	49	300ft	1013	275					
			END	RUN	10				
140700	50	300ft	1013	275					

INS roll, 560 para. → 50.
 + 700

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 503.....

Date 15.12.96.....

Page 3..... of 4.....

Video Tape	
No. <u>A503</u>	
Ends <u>1535</u>	
✓ FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	36' 29.31W	36' 28.85N
Long	2' 13.93W	2' 14.51W
Time	144045	14:41:20
Status	✓	NAV ✓

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			START	RUN	11				
140738	51	300ft	1013	210			across front		
			END	RUN	11				
142136	54	300ft	1013	210		14.1	12.2		6
			START	RUN	12				
142224	55	300ft	1013	275	181	13.9	13.4		047/3.
			END	RUN	12				
142723	56	300ft	1013	275					
			START	RUN	13				
142819	57	300ft	1013	030					
			END	RUN	13				
143818	60	300ft	1013	030					
143818									
			START	RUN	14				
143926	61	300ft	1013	275					
			END	RUN	14				
144611	63	300ft	1013	320					
			START	RUN	15				
144705	64	300ft	1013	210	14.75	13.6	13.1	light precip	359/2
145550		Precip getting heavier (to FFC)							
145854		ss 4, few white caps.							052/7.

Heimann cal at end of mapping 300ft ≈ 1450

Video Tape	
No. A503 #2	#3
Ends 1535	1835
✓ FFC / ✓ DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	36'07.38N	36'09.15
Long	2'23.46W	2'23.95
Time	151515	15:15:50
Status	✓	✓

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	WAS SST	TAT	DP	DI Htr	CAMERA	Wind/ Sea st.
			END RUN 15							
152207	68	300ft	1013.	210	14.57.	13.2				
152540		Heimann cal. (12→18)								
1520		tracking towards ship							SS 2	light precip
									SS 3/4	
					Pos (13)		36 14.64N			
			START RUN 16				.1 36.44		SS 1	
153049	69	100ft.	1013.	140	14.6	14.6	13.9		DFC	270/4
			END RUN 16							
153811	70	100ft	1013	150.						back into precip, viz pos
153815		Heimann cal							FFC	
153940		Stop Video		# 2						
153950		Start Video		# 3						
			START RUN 17							
154238	71	300ft	1013	345	16.25	13.6	c 15.3	DFC		
			END RUN 17							
155240	72.	300ft	1013.							
155243		Heimann cal (12→18)							FFC.	
			START RUN 18							
155657	73	100ft	1013.	155						SS 2 light precip
			END RUN 18							
160341	74.	100ft	1013	170						
160344		Heimann cal 12→18								

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A 503**.....

Project **OMEGA**.....

Date **15.12.96**.....

Tape No **AS03 #2**..... User ^{Swinson} **A. KAYE**.....

Retention Period **Indefinitely**.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
124146	5000	FFC / DFC	START RECORDING
124538 → 130308		"	RUN 7, 300ft 4 → 3
130613 → 132431		"	PROFILE P2 ↗, 50ft → FL150
132845 → 134007		"	RUNS 8.1, 8.2, FL150, Aries calcs
134046 → 134440		"	ORBITS 1,2,3, 50°, 60°, 55° bank.
135309 → 140110		"	RUN 9, 300ft
140202 → 140700		"	RUN 10, 300ft,
140738 → 142136		"	RUN 11, 300ft
142224 → 142723		"	RUN 12, 300ft
142819 → 143818		"	RUN 13, 300ft
143926 → 144611		"	RUN 14, 300ft
144705 → 150207		"	RUN 15, 300ft
153049 → 153811		"	RUN 16, 100ft
153940			END OF TAPE

1. PITOT PRESSURE reading 13 DRSU on preflight, has been zero for the last few flights
2. TEVM - RV display intermittent
3. HORACE - Preflight DRS data not aligned with ISS 30 Emer count on optic = 13.
4. VIDEO SWITCH: FC DISPLAY HAVE TO ADJUST CONTRAST & BRIGHTNESS EVERY TIME THE SCREEN IS CHANGED
ER DISPLAY - INTERMITTENT DISPLAY, MOSTLY BLANK.
5. FWVS: reading $\approx 24^{\circ}\text{C}$ warmer than TWC or AE
6. ICTP: " $\approx 7^{\circ}\text{C}$ warmer than DE INDE at FL210
7. AOS: very "stepped" signal at FL210
8. SATCOM: Test message to ship failed due to error code DEE
9. SAFIRE = looking straight after alt 60° ?
 58° ? maybe not, only got 58° max.
 50°
10. TWC: status light flashing at 1425 intermittently. Para 78 not responding. TAMB spiking (144955) very occasionally.
300ft in precip, TAT = 13°C .
11. Intercom: fwd cargo hold boxes - ~~to~~ very loud 400Hz type noise all the time. doesn't go when PA deselected
12. box 8, port fwd - very intermittent
13. lower BBRs up most of time

MARTIAN LOG
=====

Sheet 1 / 5

Flight No: AS03

Martian: 11H

Date: 15 / 12 / 96

093657

Take-off ETD: 0920 Z from : Valencia Landing ETA: 1730 Z into : Valencia

Pan surface : Concrete / ~~Tarmac~~ Dry / ~~Wet~~ IAT : 4-6°C at 0735 Z

Weather : 6/8 Ac (thin) Light dew condensing. ST : 10.2°C

	MARSS	Deimos
Instrument Status:	Light salt deposits on mirror Cleaned window	OK Cleaned window
Flight Action:	MUX sticky starting	Dem 7-64
Rating Mode	FERA PRT: A/B/C/D/E Pol. G.	Scan: 000 Pol: 00
Receiver Power On	07:12:	07:12:
Receiver Stable by	: :	: :
	Start time - End time	Start time - End time
Target warm-ups	: : - Should have refilled	: : - : :
Liquid Nitrogen Cal	N ₂ :LN ₂ : - Dewar (R2P3) before departure!	N ₂ LN ₂ : - : :
Ambient Calibration	08:59 : - 09:01 :	08:40:00 - 08:55 :
Ambient Target Temp	+11.8 °C +11.9 °C	+11.2 °C ↗ +11.8 °C
Power Changed Over	: : T _n 281K	T _n 282/283K.
Receiver Stable by	: :	: :

Trials Summary Amb Cal Temp measured with wire TC probe on Wavelech 2030 PVing

Interesting Qualitative experience.
Data probably u/s for surface work, due to very dense cloud + ppt. Could produce LWP's.

MARSS Motor 'froz' in rain at 1436Z (Had a 'weak pulse' on initial boot after C.P.E.O.)
Could not be reset.

Level Cal	: NONE - : :	FL
-----------	--------------	----

Flight: A503

Date: 15/12/96

Operator: TAH

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
0828		MARSS Mix needing lots of resetting. Freezing + Ramping
0920		Ground Power Changeover (LMD LEDs not staying ON as long as usual) But sensor looks OK Take off Valencia
0954		MARSS Gains + T _b 's mod after T/O Reset did nothing Rebooting LMD did the trick
0957		Gains stabilising quickly! But Ci will cover sky before cal can be done
101720	Pls FL210 ↓	Through ice cloud. Ci above. Small Ci field below Zen T _b 's ^{both} decreases during profile below cloud.
102219	Pl; FLOGO	↓ Could be cal? Mirror condensation?
103342	Plc "	Chot 157 dipped ~0.3 counts/K Cosy Plot.
1037		SOGM2 "V" decreasing faster than "H" on profile
104624	Plc 50'	"Showers ahead?" Plot n24 v Radalt → few K bias at 300' n50 ~ 3 K n80 ~ 1 K n157 ~ 0 K
105113	Rls. At 10 300'	Big Spikes in nadir T _b 's under T _b 's (at T2 + UBBR)
110140		Crossing Almera front Overcast. No noticeable change in underlying T _b nad at 24 + SOG 89: 200-195 157 252-247 155-157 202-200 ∴ Cloud above
1117	SS2	Ref. of A/C in SS at ~1113 Low SS

Flight: AS03

Date: 15/12/96 Operator: R.H.

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
1117	SS2	Noise at Deimos T _b 's just halved!
1109-1119		Ben T _b 's have be flat (57K + 145K)
112246	R1e (Pt9) 300'	
112421	R2s 300'	Tzen still flat (55 + 144K)
1129		Aerosol increasing (∴ W/S ↑) STOWS
113404	R2e (Pt8) 300'	Small step inc in N24 (~2K) not SOC
113457	R3s SS2	
114121		White caps spotted, coinc. with N24 ↑ 2-3K
1146		(Low level cloud (var) above)
1142-1147	RFI	from Tx. Some floatam SS2
115700	R3e (Pt7)	1156. N24 + N55 ↑ 6K. Clouds building above
		Funnel cloud sighted Ben T _b 's ↑
115840	R4s	Jump ~1K in ST after Cal. Small increase at 800 near coast
120751	R4e? (Pt6) 300'	Slight rain T _b 's ↑
120840	R5s SS3	Regular white caps out of pm,
1207		MARSS PRT MUX Froze
1219	SS1	
1220		RESET MARSS CPU
1225		DEIMOS T _b 's noisy
		"Oily" warm tongue Surface structure + SST jump
		It is oil! No increase in R ₂ Deimos T _b 's
1231		287 = 70 2157 = 172 189 = 203 1157 = 256 T _{SE} 15°C =
1233		Classy appearance gone Textured odd ↓
123405	R5e 300' (Pt5)	Uniform (homogenous) Cloud above
123545	R6s	
124140		Turbulence increasing MARSS T _Z ↑
124424	R6e Pt4?	

415

light: AS03 Date: 15/12/96 Operator: JWH

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
124548	R7s (H-L) 300'	PPT stopped
130308 130254	R7e (W of Pt 3)	Rain falling
		{ Last time for a post lunch slump. But no lunch yet! }
130613	P2s. 30'	SS2 QNH 1013 hPa. thru' cloud.
	2400'	Cu tops
1306	Change to 1000%	Maine Band Tx do not cause RFI
132431	P2e FL150	Clear above.
132845	R8s FL150	MARSS CPU reset. (Froze since 1245!)
133343	R8.1e "	Clear above, but too low for MARSS cal
133518	R8.2s "	Reciprocal for L.W. cal.
	R8.2e	
134106?	O1s. +50°	
	O2 +60°	No trees - eyes closed!
	O3 +55°	
1359		Rain falling
140110	R9e 300'	
140202	R10s	
140700	R10e	MARSS ok.
140748	R10s	
141050	SS2	Crossed a line of flotsam Homogeneous Cloud Above
141805		light rpt
142224	R11s	" to mod. T _{pt} ↑ 157 Subtracted. 89 ↑ 265K
142723	R12e	
142819	R13s	Still in Rain 150 almost at 124 knot!
1436		Step in 150 ↑ 10K front?
143818	R13e	MARSS Motor Stuck Cannot reset
144611	R14e	MARSS still stuck
144709	R15s	Power down LMD box for 10mins + retry
		Fairing that, I'll shut MARSS down +
		Reset all PSLs

Light: AS03

Date: 15/12/96 Operator: JH.

Time	Run Label	Status/Remarks
1459		SS4 now whitecaps. Powered MARSS Rf ↓
150207	R15e	All PSU LEDs lit
150806		Didn't help! Now in Continuous ppt. Deimos Δ Pol drops under showers
151837	SS2	No whitecaps Vis ↑
152045	SS1	
152343	SS3-4	
152841	1013 SS2	Dropped to 100'
153049	R16s 100'	to Dreefly ship. Skies above clearer
153432	SS1	Deimos Th's flat (hor)
154800		2D-C : S/L
155240	R17e	Short of ship to allow cal
155657	R18s SS2 100'	QNH 1013.2 light ppt.
160341	R18e 100'	At ship.
160939	R18s SS2 50'	QNH 1013
		Transit back at FL220 Under clear skies above S _e over land, But MARSS WCD still U/S ⇒ No Cal. Pass
	Land	Valencia

Time (GMT)	Event mark	Run no.	Height	Filter posn.	Mir-ror posn.	Shutter status		Hor link (tick)	Temp diff Ref-BB	Sol Zen	Comments
						up	low				
073000				0123	NADIR	C	0				HOT TARGET CAL BOOTED AS03-1.PRE.
073300				0123	NADIR	C	0				HOT CAL START 329/300
074400											end HOT CAL.
074600				0123	COLD	C	0				COLD CAL START 286/300.
075000											end COLD CAL
075100				0123	NADIR	C	0				SW CAL START
080100											end SW CAL.
080300				0123	HOT	C	0				HOT CAL START 319/300
082500											end HOT CAL.
											MORACE & PC recording stopped.
094500											AS03-1.FLT BOOTED
094800				0123	HOT	C	C				HOT CAL start / Transit 316/300.
											Curtis prevents gain or orbit cal.
101015								768			
101050								800			
101200				0123	COLD	C	C				COLD CAL start 291/300.
103300											ASP heater off.
104500				01	NADIR	C	C				setup for first run.

FIREFIRE OPERATOR'S LOG

Flight Number: A503.

Operators name: J. CRAWFORD

Date: 15 DEC 96

Page 4 of 5

Time (GMT)	Event mark	Run no.	Height	Filter posn.	Mirror posn.	Shutter status		Hor link (tick)	Temp diff Ref-BB	Sol Zen	Comments
						up	low				
140736 142136		11	300	2	N	C	O				run 11 start end 11
142224 142600 142713		12	300	2	N	C	O				run 12 start shutter closed via panel. end
142819		13				C	C				in panel ↓
144705		15	300	2	N	C	C				
144900 145800		15	300	2	N	C	O				SST run 15. shutter closed / panel.
152030			300	2	N	C	O				open shutter - approaching Discovery
153049 153811		16	300	2	N	C	O				run 16 start end 16
154238 155240		17	300	2	N	C	O				run 17 start end 17.
155657 160341 160430		18	100	2	N	C	O				run 18 start end 18 shutter closed.
											Scan mirror lost with 15 plates Scan mirror ^{jammed} non-operative.

P.S.A.P Log

Flight No. A503.....

Date 15.12.96.....

Project OMEGA.....

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	B _a x 10 ⁻⁶ Start of Run	Height	Run	B _a x 10 ⁻⁶ End of Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time ✓	New filter Tr = 1.000 ✓	Set to 2.6 lpm	37.0	Levels 39 1.55	Ave = 30 s	48.3	← Preflight ONLY $T_r = 0.984$
0945	0.998	2.55	0.0	300 →			CLUB AT
1048	0.988	2.62	5.0 x 10 ⁻⁶	500'			
105113	0.985	2.62	2.2 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	1		RUN STARTS
1105	0.978	2.62	2.6 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	1		
112431	0.964	2.62	3.4 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	2		RUN STARTS
113457	0.952	2.61	3.9 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	3		RUN STARTS
115840	0.941	2.60	0.7 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	4		RUN STARTS
120840	0.940	2.6	0.6 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	5		RUN STARTS
1219	0.938	2.6	2.2 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	5		
123545	0.932	2.6	0.0 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	6		RUN STARTS
124538	0.928	2.59	1.1 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	7		RUN STARTS
135309	0.924	2.62	0.7 x 10 ⁻⁶	300'	9		RUN STARTS

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ Start of Run	Height	Run	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$ End of Run	Remarks
140738	0.915	2.60	3.7×10^{-6}	300'	11		
1434	0.913	2.60	0.5×10^{-6}	300'			
144705	0.906	2.60	2.4×10^{-6}	300'	15		
1528	0.895	2.61	4.3×10^{-6}	300'			
153049	0.894	2.61	0.3×10^{-6}	100'	16		
154238	0.892	2.58	1.1×10^{-6}	300'	17		
1620	0.887	2.53 2.53	3.5×10^{-6}	→	PROFILE		
163511	0.891	2.63	0	FL220	19		START RUN
1655	0.894	3.04	0.0	↓			SOOTY OFF

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A503

Date: 15/12/96

Operator: MFP

Page 5 of 7

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	
141600	70	0.14	0.6	20			0.5	600	1			
141700	50	0.13	0.2	15			1	650	1			
141800												
141900												end of Run
142000												Start Run 12 @ 300'
142100	105	0.17	0.4	25			6	400	1			
142200	450	0.19	0.9	25			17	725	1			
142300	390	0.32	3	30			50	500	1			
142400												
142500												end of Run
142600												Start Run 13 @ 300'
142700	240	0.3	3.9	35			35	800	1			
142800	305	0.3	5	40			89	700	1			
142900	210	0.2	6	35			47	725	1			
143000	280	0.1	9	35			9	800	1			
143100	700	0.12	2	45			40	800	1			
143200												
143300												end of Run
143400												Start Run 14 @ 300'
143500	570	0.12	2	25			10	800	1			
143600	430	0.09	1	25			3	800	1			
143700	540	0.10	2	35			11	800	1			
143800												
143900												end of Run
144000												Start Run 15 @ 300'
144100	250	0.10	0.4	25			0.5	700	1			
144200	1000	0.09	1.1	25			2	800	1			
144300	226	0.13	0.9	20			4	600	1			
144400	240	0.21	1.6	30			15	700	1			
144500												
144600												
144700												
144800												
144900												
145000												
145100												
145200												
145300												
145400												
145500												
145600												
145700												
145800												
145900												
150000												
150100												
150200												
150300												
150400												
150500												
150600												
150700												
150800												
150900												
151000												
151100												
151200												
151300												
151400												
151500												
151600												
151700												
151800												
151900												
152000												
152100												
152200												
152300												
152400												
152500												
152600												
152700												
152800												
152900												
153000												
153100	205	0.09	0.4	15								
153200	110	0.12	0.9	25			3	600	1			
153300	220	0.11	1.7	20			11	400	1			
153400	105	0.2	2	30			7	500	1			
153500												
153600												
153700												
153800												
153900												
154000												
154100												
154200												
154300	140	0.2	3	30			8	450	1			
154400	150	0.3	1	30			9	800	1			

Get in Notes due to Run
missing Air cond in JMS
Start Run 16 @ 100'

end of Run
Start Run 17 @ 300'

DATE A 503 TI MRF _____

1013-8.

160/015
NAV _____

B04 LAT/EL
ENH _____

AIRFIELD _____

AIRFIELD _____

R/W 20 W/V CALM TEMP 17 QNH 1013 QFE _____

R/W 080 W/V 08 TEMP _____ QNH 1013 QFE _____

WX _____

WX BWVA

ATC CL L ALC 2360 ↑ 120 ^{124.75} / ₂₃

ATC CL → 4000

T/O TIME 0937

LAND TIME 1110

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1017 ²⁰	014	25	280	185	250	270/50	F210		N36524 W0112	P1
32 ¹⁹							F60		N37292 E00525	—
33 ¹²							↘		N37277 E00541	—
56 ²⁸							50'		N36536 E00473	—
1051 ¹³	32	25	181	178	180	190/14	300'		N36436 E00491	R1
1122 ⁴⁴									N38010 E00258	—
24 ³¹	198	25	182	182	185/8	300			N35581 E0029.7	R2
34 ²²									N37288 E00405	—
34 ⁵⁷	141	25	184	176	180	012/06	300		N37261 E00395	R3
51 ⁰⁰									N36328 E00137	—
58 ⁴⁴	241	15	181	183	235/12	320			N36297 E0010.1	R4
1207 ⁵¹									N36155 E00175	—
08 ⁴⁶	324	35	180	183	205/10	300			N36176 W0020.6	R5
34 ⁰⁵									N37195 W0018.5	—
35 ⁴⁵	216	186	177	180	014/7	300			N37175 W0123.3	R6
44 ²²									N36555 W01443	—
45 ⁵⁵	141	180	180	180	014/7	300			N36094 W01400	R7
1303 ⁰²									N36098 W01037	—
06 ¹³							50'		N36095 W01120	P2
24 ³¹									N36251 W0049	—
1328 ⁴²	123	266	180	220	267/4	150			N36187 W02083	R8.1
33 ⁵⁵									N38080 W01451	—
35 ⁰⁹	277	15	193	182	235	272/39	150		N36046 W01460	R8.2

N36069 W02048 —

2501

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT / LONG	RUN
40 ⁰⁷	020								N 36092 W 02066	01
	080									02
	120									03
53 ⁰⁹	028	1P	181	182	185	168/00	300		N 36159 W 01307	R9.
401 ⁰									N 37376 W 01161	—
02 ⁰²	267			180	182	262/02	300		N 36394 W 01177	R10
07 ⁰⁰									N 36390 W 01367	—
17 ⁵¹	208	1P	178	182	185	243/06	300		N 36377 W 01384	R11
21 ³⁰									N 36006 W 02027	—
22 ²³	260	1S	189	180	185	024/06	300		N 35592 W 02052	R12
27 ²³									N 35587 W 02247	—
28 ¹⁹	02	1P	183	180	185	078/07	300		N 36005 W 02259	R13
38 ¹⁸									N 36274 W 02077	—
39 ²⁴	266	1P	181	180	180	347/06	300		N 36295 W 02093	R14
46 ¹¹									N 36352 W 02377	—
47 ⁰⁵	206	0	185	180	182	333/3	300		N 36346 W 02338	R15
1502 ⁰⁷									N 35515 W 03001	—
30 ⁴⁹	138	1P	185	180	183	273/8	1000		N 36261 W 01490	R16
38 ¹¹									N 36076 W 01327	R16
42 ³⁰	341	2P	181	180	181	082/07	300		N 36016 W 01311	R17
52 ⁴⁰									N 36298 W 01448	—
56 ⁵⁷	153	0	181	181	185	239/4	100		N 36313 W 01476	R18
1603 ⁴									N 36117 W 01376	—
09 ³⁹	024	0	181	181	188	078/9	500		N 36099 W 01379	R19
35 ¹¹	008	2S	181	180	255	273/37	F220		N 37345 W 00501	R18
55 ⁰⁵									N 38584 W 00341	—

A503 15-DEC-96 10:07:09 007 -- 37.63 -0.20 AS P

198. 447. 21.0 298. -22.1 -21.6 277/30

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A503

15-DEC-96

10:10:12

007

37.38

-0.23 AS P

197.	447.	21.0	302.	-22.1	-21.5	275/33
------	------	------	------	-------	-------	--------

PRESS -G- 22.00 447.70

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A503

15-DEC-96

10:44:48

010

36.97

0.77 AS P

ALT	BARO	WIND	TEMP	TOT	DEW	WIND
feet	hPa	kts	degrees	C	C	deg/s
175.	995.	0.5	187.	14.5	12.8	257/2

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

0

PCASP CONC	#/cc	559
PCASP MEAN RAD	um	0.1
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	15.73

FSSP CONC	#/cc	1
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	2.5
FSSP LMC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	um	0
2D-C LMC	g/m3	0.000e+000

96-12-15 10:46:27

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1
1

0.1
0.1

10
10

A503

15-DEC-96

11:21:48

013

37.98

-0.39 FC P

TEMP	HEAT	WIND	WIND	WIND	WIND	WIND
317.	1004.	0.2	180.	14.6	9.7	064/6

PSAP LOG

1148.00

PSAP TRA

0.96

4095.00

3412.50

2730.00

2047.50

1365.00

682.50

0.00

1.00

0.83

0.67

0.50

0.33

0.17

0.00

1030

1040

1050

1100

1110

1120

POWER UP CHECK -- OK : K/B 01899/R3.02

A503 15-DEC-96 11:25:45 016 Ω 37.90 -0.51 FC P

HGG deg	SPR m	PHGT k	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
195.	1003.	0.3	187.	14.7	10.2	346 / 2

PSAP LIN 0.29 PSAP TRA 0.96

POWER UP CHECK -- OK : K/B 01899/A3.02

A503

15-DEC-96

11:41:30

018

37.17

-0.42 FC P

QFE m	QNH m	QFE kPa	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
141.	1004.	0.3	184.	15.1	10.6	021 / 4

S. TEMP
C

16.00

WIND
m/s

3.00

POWER UP CHECK -- OK : K/B 01899/A3.02

A503

15-DEC-96

11:47:51

018

36.92

-0.16 AS P

TEMP	PRES	WIND	WAVE	SEA	WIND
deg C	hPa	kmph	cm	cm	deg / s
136.	1004.	0.2	181.	15.1	12.8
					161 / 1

S. TEMP 15.02 175.02

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

0

PCASP CONC	#/cc	92
PCASP MEAN RAD	um	0.1
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	0.71
FSSP CONC	#/cc	0
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	2.0
FSSP LAC	gm/m3	0.00
2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	um	0
2D-C LAC	g/m3	0.000e+000

96-12-15 12:00:33

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

A503 15-DEC-96 12:13:30 023 -- 36.49 -0.54 AS P

321.	1004.	0.3	186.	14.9	13.5	230/4
------	-------	-----	------	------	------	-------

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	DEVICE	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

PCASP CONC/cc

1000

PCASP CONC	#/cc	485
PCASP MEAN RAD	um	0.1
PCASP MASS	ug/m3	5.30

FSSP CONC	#/cc	2
FSSP MEAN RAD	u	2.4
FSSP LHC	gm/m3	0.00

2D-C CONC	#/l	0.0
2D-C MAX SIZE	um	0
2D-C LHC	g/m3	0.000e+000

96-12-15 12:18:48

PCASP COUNT FSSP COUNT

1000
1000

1	0.1	10
1	0.1	10

A503

15-DEC-96

13:05:24

031

--

36.15

-1.20 AS P

281.

1007.

0.2

185.

14.5

12.6

215/2

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	DEVICE	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A503 15-DEC-96 13:23:33 035 36.41 -2.33 AS P

284. 593. 14.1 223. -7.3 -8.5 274/23

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

ADG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
7.	1003.	0.3	184.	14.2	13.8	190 / 3

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

A503 15-DEC-96 14:40:06 061 36.50 -2.23 AS P

TIME	0.00	PRET	TIME	TIME	TIME
268.	1002.	0.3	183.	13.8	14.1
					344/ 4

S. TEMP 15.28

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	VIDEO	HELP

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A503

GPS data
06:40:30 - 17:20:27

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<p>1 9 1 1</p>	<p>Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log</p>
<p>1 2 4 3</p>	<p>Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)</p>
<p>5 5</p>	<p>SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log</p>
<p>1 7 1</p>	<p>^{PSAP} Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)</p>
<p>✓ ✓ ✓ ✓</p>	<p>Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track</p>

A503 15-DEC-96 10:17:20-16:35:11GMT

INS TRACK - run 06

INS TRACK - run 06

A503 15-DEC-96

P1 FL210-50ft(101720-104624) + P2 50'-FL150(130613-132431)

A503 15-DEC-96

P3 50'-FL220(160939-163511)

A503 15-DEC-96 P1 FL210-50ft From 101720-104624 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:45

A503 15-DEC-96 P1 FL210-50ft From 101720-104624 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:45

A503 15-DEC-96 P2 50'-FL150 From 130613-132431 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:08

A503 15-DEC-96 P2 50'-FL150 From 130613-132431 Potted 20-Jan-1997 16:08

A503 15-DEC-96 P3 50'-FL220 From 160939-163511 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:28

A503 15-DEC-96 P3 50'-FL220 From 160939-163511 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:28

A503 15-DEC-96 R1 300' From 105113-112246 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:48

A503 15-DEC-96 R1 300' From 105113-112246 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:49

A503 15-DEC-96 R2 300' From 112431-113404 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:51

A503 15-DEC-96 R2 300' From 112431-113404 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:51

A503 15-DEC-96 R3 300' From 113457-115700 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:54

A503 15-DEC-96 R3 300' From 113457-115700 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:54

A503 15-DEC-96 R4 300' From 115840-120751 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:56

A503 15-DEC-96 R4 300' From 115840-120751 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:56

A503 15-DEC-96 R5 300' From 120840-123405 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:00

A503 15-DEC-96 R5 300' From 120840-123405 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:00

A503 15-DEC-96 R6 300' From 123545-124424 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:02

A503 15-DEC-96 R6 300' From 123545 - 124424 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:02

A503 15-DEC-96 R7 300' From 124538-130308 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:05

A503 15-DEC-96 R7 300' From 124538-130308 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:05

A503 15-DEC-96 R9 300' From 135309-140110 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:10

A503 15-DEC-96 R9 300' From 135309-140110 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:10

A503 15-DEC-96 R10 300' From 140202 - 140700 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:11

A503 15-DEC-96 R10 300' From 140202-140700 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:11

A503 15-DEC-96 R11 300' From 140738 - 142136 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:13

A503 15-DEC-96 R11 300' From 140738-142136 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:13

A503 15-DEC-96 R12 300' From 142224-142723 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:15

A503 15-DEC-96 R12 300' From 142224-142723 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:15

A503 15-DEC-96 R13 300' From 142819-143818 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:16

A503 15-DEC-96 R13 300' From 142819-143818 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:17

A503 15-DEC-96 R14 300' From 143926-144611 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:18

A503 15-DEC-96 R14 300' From 143926-144611 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:18

A503 15-DEC-96 R15 300' From 144705-150207 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:20

A503 15-DEC-96 R15 300' From 144705-150207 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:20

A503 15-DEC-96 R16 300' From 153049-153811 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:22

A503 15-DEC-96 R16 300' From 153049-153811 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:22

A503 15-DEC-96 R17 300' From 154238-155240 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:23

A503 15-DEC-96 R17 300' From 154238-155240 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:23

A503 15-DEC-96 R18 300' From 155657-160341 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:25

A503 15-DEC-96 R18 30' From 155657-160341 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:25

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 1003.31
 Standard dev 0.585441
 Max value 1004.47
 Min value 1001.08

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 288.162
 Standard dev 0.308368
 Max value 288.707
 Min value 287.544

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 284.181
 Standard dev 1.45277
 Max value 287.124
 Min value 282.336

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 32.3834
 Standard dev 3.32833
 Max value 38.3307
 Min value 22.1201

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 413.894
 Standard dev 561.443
 Max value 3292.10
 Min value 289.044

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 287.891
 Standard dev 0.302215
 Max value 288.398
 Min value 287.233

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 94.1630
 Standard dev 5.07618
 Max value 112.275
 Min value 83.6533

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 37.3814
 Standard dev 0.375939
 Max value 38.0205
 Min value 36.7275

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 0.144009
 Standard dev 2.80512
 Max value 0.818852
 Min value -120.899

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 1.45989
 Standard dev 5.90830
 Max value 8.84103
 Min value -237.444

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1894
 Mean -2.72406
 Standard dev 4.24878
 Max value 158.906
 Min value -7.49901

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1894
 Mean -14.9859
 Standard dev 2.10626
 Max value -13.2711
 Min value -103.434

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1892
 Mean 3.95950
 Standard dev 1.93059
 Max value 9.03534
 Min value 0.854189

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 118.188

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1894
 Mean 93.7629
 Standard dev 1.51630
 Max value 97.6151
 Min value 90.1342

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 322.368

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 574
 Mean 1003.18
 Standard dev 0.147776
 Max value 1003.45
 Min value 1002.65

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 574
 Mean 287.134
 Standard dev 0.323511
 Max value 287.923
 Min value 286.620

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 574
 Mean 282.549
 Standard dev 0.644483
 Max value 283.730
 Min value 280.326

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 574
 Mean 28.6111
 Standard dev 2.19257
 Max value 33.7962
 Min value 23.5683

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 574
 Mean 289.777
 Standard dev 0.119273
 Max value 290.015
 Min value 289.439

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 574
 Mean 286.874
 Standard dev 0.330205
 Max value 287.675
 Min value 286.366

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 574
 Mean 94.2430
 Standard dev 1.91818
 Max value 100.566
 Min value 91.0874

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 574
 Mean 37.7267
 Standard dev 0.141330
 Max value 37.9700
 Min value 37.4825

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 574
 Mean -0.583651
 Standard dev 5.119098e-02
 Max value -0.495327
 Min value -0.674075

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 574
 Mean -4.89805
 Standard dev 0.889420
 Max value -2.31173
 Min value -6.75755

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 574
 Mean -0.445384
 Standard dev 1.85073
 Max value 1.72788
 Min value -5.39525

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 574
 Mean -14.5220
 Standard dev 0.367862
 Max value -13.6549
 Min value -15.5742

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 574
 Mean 5.29560
 Standard dev 0.596150
 Max value 6.79316
 Min value 2.95699

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 5.19568

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 574
 Mean 94.4330
 Standard dev 0.855321
 Max value 96.1146
 Min value 91.9220

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 196.233

A503 15-DEC-96 R3 300' From 113457-115700 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:54

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 1324
Mean 1003.35
Standard dev 0.236998
Max value 1004.03
Min value 1002.89

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 1324
Mean 288.003
Standard dev 0.310909
Max value 288.482
Min value 287.106

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 1324
Mean 284.651
Standard dev 1.33091
Max value 287.167
Min value 282.044

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 1324
Mean 33.2133
Standard dev 3.10939
Max value 38.5378
Min value 23.3604

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 1324
Mean 289.731
Standard dev 0.441920
Max value 290.536
Min value 288.621

POT TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 1324
Mean 287.728
Standard dev 0.321105
Max value 288.221
Min value 286.818

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 1324
Mean 90.1498
Standard dev 2.18155
Max value 94.0610
Min value 83.4674

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 1324
Mean 36.9679
Standard dev 1.04790
Max value 37.4404
Min value -7.241485e-03

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 1324
Mean -0.111777
Standard dev 3.86069
Max value 139.935
Min value -0.662025

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1324
Mean -2.64543
Standard dev 2.37541
Max value 0.465347
Min value -53.5293

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1324
Mean 1.37970
Standard dev 3.99793
Max value 111.694
Min value -1.74300

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 1324
Mean -14.5935
Standard dev 2.15630
Max value 62.0585
Min value -15.9355

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 1322
Mean 4.12685
Standard dev 1.38175
Max value 6.94004
Min value 0.903291

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 332.456

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 1324
Mean 93.8923
Standard dev 1.26467
Max value 96.3492
Min value 90.6845

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 141.305

A503 15-DEC-96 R4 300' From 115840-120751 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 15:56

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 552
Mean 1002.95
Standard dev 8.16779
Max value 1003.54
Min value 811.428

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 552
Mean 288.240
Standard dev 0.119867
Max value 288.396
Min value 287.963

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 552
Mean 286.148
Standard dev 0.575099
Max value 287.118
Min value 284.692

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 552
Mean 40.3290
Standard dev 19.3330
Max value 493.090
Min value 34.5562

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 552
Mean 290.024
Standard dev 8.972626e-02
Max value 290.208
Min value 289.804

POT TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 552
Mean 288.001
Standard dev 0.775558
Max value 305.963
Min value 287.684

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 552
Mean 86.2812
Standard dev 73.8699
Max value 1818.49
Min value 81.1205

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 552
Mean 36.3415
Standard dev 1.14033
Max value 36.4974
Min value 9.63924

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 552
Mean -3.584277e-02
Standard dev 0.658560
Max value 15.0743
Min value -0.293822

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 552
Mean 2.85938
Standard dev 5.35722
Max value 127.726
Min value 0.828728

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 552
Mean 3.86695
Standard dev 1.08217
Max value 4.89127
Min value -19.8025

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 552
Mean -14.3872
Standard dev 1.19042
Max value 12.6023
Min value -15.2363

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 550
Mean 4.75109
Standard dev 0.392046
Max value 5.65755
Min value 3.49940

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 233.519

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 552
Mean 93.9090
Standard dev 0.449079
Max value 95.1244
Min value 92.4961

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 239.587

A503 15-DEC-96 R5 300' From 120840-123405 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:00

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1526
Mean 1003.38
Standard dev 0.209545
Max value 1004.17
Min value 1002.89

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1526
Mean 288.008
Standard dev 0.165690
Max value 288.589
Min value 287.658

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1526
Mean 285.098
Standard dev 1.76766
Max value 287.718
Min value 280.545

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1526
Mean 36.1566
Standard dev 3.35790
Max value 42.0648
Min value 18.7755

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1526
Mean 444.543
Standard dev 625.055
Max value 3292.10
Min value 72.5054

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1526
Mean 287.731
Standard dev 0.162608
Max value 288.309
Min value 287.366

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1526
Mean 87.3834
Standard dev 2.79675
Max value 94.2469
Min value 79.9362

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1526
Mean 36.7852
Standard dev 0.750485
Max value 37.3261
Min value 9.86757

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1526
Mean -0.807518
Standard dev 0.505182
Max value 15.4383
Min value -1.30805

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1526
Mean 2.08197
Standard dev 2.17469
Max value 40.0773
Min value -1.76398

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1526
Mean -0.769461
Standard dev 3.56719
Max value 6.24933
Min value -6.29549

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1526
Mean -14.2679
Standard dev 0.383524
Max value -12.9387
Min value -15.5903

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1526
Mean 4.29845
Standard dev 1.68235
Max value 7.14739
Min value 0.119090

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 159.717

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1526
Mean 93.7323
Standard dev 0.972685
Max value 95.9531
Min value 91.3625

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 323.103

A503 15-DEC-96 R6 300' From 123545-124424 Plotted 20-Jan-1997 16:02

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 520
Mean 1002.92
Standard dev 0.693551
Max value 1004.34
Min value 1001.17

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 520
Mean 287.823
Standard dev 0.259692
Max value 288.269
Min value 287.263

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 520
Mean 283.757
Standard dev 1.12973
Max value 288.075
Min value 280.107

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 520
Mean 32.8385
Standard dev 2.30282
Max value 37.6752
Min value 26.9158

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 520
Mean 289.267
Standard dev 0.167088
Max value 289.603
Min value 288.939

POT TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 520
Mean 287.583
Standard dev 0.222258
Max value 288.014
Min value 287.156

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 520
Mean 88.1352
Standard dev 5.32705
Max value 100.380
Min value 75.6617

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 520
Mean 37.1085
Standard dev 0.106133
Max value 37.2921
Min value 36.9260

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 520
Mean -1.56164
Standard dev 0.100333
Max value -1.38983
Min value -1.73805

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 520
Mean -4.33222
Standard dev 1.27620
Max value -1.16910
Min value -7.06178

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 520
Mean -3.06763
Standard dev 0.631606
Max value -1.28253
Min value -4.75206

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 520
Mean -13.9133
Standard dev 0.513377
Max value -11.3895
Min value -15.2346

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 520
Mean 5.43162
Standard dev 0.837304
Max value 7.67058
Min value 3.92213

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 35.3022

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 520
Mean 93.9429
Standard dev 1.09076
Max value 96.1445
Min value 91.3969

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 217.307

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 1002.11
 Standard dev 0.232107
 Max value 1002.88
 Min value 1001.10

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 287.445
 Standard dev 0.126858
 Max value 287.685
 Min value 286.886

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 285.728
 Standard dev 0.503057
 Max value 286.632
 Min value 284.030

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 34.8803
 Standard dev 5.99283
 Max value 44.2896
 Min value 24.6270

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 288.607
 Standard dev 0.257430
 Max value 289.429
 Min value 288.229

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 287.272
 Standard dev 0.131806
 Max value 287.532
 Min value 286.694

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 93.9141
 Standard dev 2.24717
 Max value 100.380
 Min value 86.0694

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 36.2091
 Standard dev 3.37255
 Max value 36.8725
 Min value 4.637946e-03

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean -1.36780
 Standard dev 0.227875
 Max value -1.528084e-03
 Min value -1.71675

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1043
 Mean 1.82274
 Standard dev 0.788585
 Max value 3.76358
 Min value -0.682282

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1043
 Mean 3.41201
 Standard dev 1.97328
 Max value 6.79781
 Min value -1.29607

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 1043
 Mean -13.8437
 Standard dev 0.401395
 Max value -12.7316
 Min value -14.9799

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 1039
 Mean 4.08715
 Standard dev 1.64441
 Max value 7.56461
 Min value 0.330149

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 241.888

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 1051
 Mean 93.8951
 Standard dev 1.18010
 Max value 96.9589
 Min value 91.6862

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 143.341

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 482
 Mean 1001.94
 Standard dev 0.528890
 Max value 1003.31
 Min value 1001.19

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 482
 Mean 287.424
 Standard dev 7.965665e-02
 Max value 287.568
 Min value 287.247

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 482
 Mean 288.008
 Standard dev 5.93412
 Max value 308.160
 Min value 285.100

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 482
 Mean 39.2569
 Standard dev 1.47358
 Max value 42.8062
 Min value 32.2117

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 482
 Mean 773.482
 Standard dev 1027.68
 Max value 3292.06
 Min value 288.339

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 482
 Mean 287.265
 Standard dev 5.155768e-02
 Max value 287.363
 Min value 287.129

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 482
 Mean 88.6944
 Standard dev 4.58971
 Max value 95.7337
 Min value 76.4051

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 482
 Mean 36.4394
 Standard dev 0.108827
 Max value 36.6267
 Min value 36.2509

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 482
 Mean -1.39166
 Standard dev 6.982874e-02
 Max value -1.27094
 Min value -1.51200

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 482
 Mean 4.72706
 Standard dev 0.409446
 Max value 5.84452
 Min value 3.57893

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 482
 Mean 3.749499e-03
 Standard dev 0.303286
 Max value 0.835983
 Min value -0.673439

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 482
 Mean -12.9592
 Standard dev 0.746778
 Max value -10.8427
 Min value -14.5089

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 482
 Mean 4.73689
 Standard dev 0.407959
 Max value 5.84851
 Min value 3.60881

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 180.045

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 482
 Mean 94.1533
 Standard dev 1.04162
 Max value 96.4059
 Min value 91.7994

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 27.4006

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 1000.95
 Standard dev 0.331451
 Max value 1002.14
 Min value 1000.30

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 287.216
 Standard dev 4.792011e-02
 Max value 287.336
 Min value 287.120

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 285.719
 Standard dev 0.582137
 Max value 286.753
 Min value 284.897

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 30.6918
 Standard dev 4.90323
 Max value 39.8946
 Min value 20.0858

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 288.572
 Standard dev 0.167607
 Max value 288.856
 Min value 288.288

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 287.139
 Standard dev 4.550963e-02
 Max value 287.285
 Min value 287.054

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 96.0010
 Standard dev 3.05742
 Max value 102.424
 Min value 86.9986

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 36.6542
 Standard dev 2.694804e-03
 Max value 36.6580
 Min value 36.6501

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 299
 Mean -1.45201
 Standard dev 9.183170e-02
 Max value -1.29387
 Min value -1.60959

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 1.32714
 Standard dev 0.843348
 Max value 2.78510
 Min value 9.231567e-04

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 299
 Mean -1.49683
 Standard dev 0.568052
 Max value -0.340828
 Min value -2.70609

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 299
 Mean -13.0508
 Standard dev 0.426353
 Max value -12.1525
 Min value -14.2879

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 2.14020
 Standard dev 0.673280
 Max value 3.38311
 Min value 0.693513

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 131.561

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 299
 Mean 94.0117
 Standard dev 1.33684
 Max value 96.8655
 Min value 91.5490

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 268.312

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 1001.04
 Standard dev 0.247134
 Max value 1001.63
 Min value 1000.29

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 287.392
 Standard dev 0.167243
 Max value 287.682
 Min value 287.072

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 285.406
 Standard dev 0.562292
 Max value 286.551
 Min value 284.030

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 39.0975
 Standard dev 3.53547
 Max value 42.8550
 Min value 17.8315

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 289.580
 Standard dev 0.882227
 Max value 290.932
 Min value 288.527

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 287.307
 Standard dev 0.169444
 Max value 287.589
 Min value 286.990

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 93.0637
 Standard dev 1.91261
 Max value 99.8224
 Min value 86.9986

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 36.3246
 Standard dev 0.179821
 Max value 36.6326
 Min value 36.0111

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 839
 Mean -1.98741
 Standard dev 4.25774
 Max value -1.63979
 Min value -125.122

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 0.772288
 Standard dev 2.47622
 Max value 68.4802
 Min value -0.752296

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 5.784149e-02
 Standard dev 2.72827
 Max value 2.07508
 Min value -67.8511

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 839
 Mean -12.5704
 Standard dev 1.88471
 Max value 40.8904
 Min value -14.0956

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 837
 Mean 1.62245
 Standard dev 0.676128
 Max value 2.86119
 Min value 7.771850e-02

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 184.283

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 839
 Mean 94.4576
 Standard dev 1.08721
 Max value 97.6841
 Min value 91.4072

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 207.969

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STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 300
Mean 1001.10
Standard dev 0.290179
Max value 1001.84
Min value 1000.50

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 300
Mean 286.729
Standard dev 0.209072
Max value 287.049
Min value 286.335

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 300
Mean 287.011
Standard dev 0.259652
Max value 287.475
Min value 286.340

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 300
Mean 39.4629
Standard dev 0.991149
Max value 41.7646
Min value 36.4783

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 300
Mean 290.552
Standard dev 7.935572e-02
Max value 290.712
Min value 290.388

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 300
Mean 286.640
Standard dev 0.226249
Max value 286.982
Min value 286.198

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 300
Mean 93.4043
Standard dev 1.98583
Max value 99.0790
Min value 87.3703

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 300
Mean 35.9832
Standard dev 2.549387e-03
Max value 35.9879
Min value 35.9784

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 300
Mean -2.24674
Standard dev 9.404190e-02
Max value -2.08463
Min value -2.40911

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 300
Mean -1.43312
Standard dev 0.648599
Max value -0.149551
Min value -3.20058

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 300
Mean -3.90186
Standard dev 0.421931
Max value -2.92313
Min value -4.83660

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 300
Mean -12.6020
Standard dev 0.369592
Max value -11.4660
Min value -13.9661

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 300
Mean 4.21561
Standard dev 0.322594
Max value 4.88795
Min value 3.28737

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 69.8322

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 300
Mean 94.6100
Standard dev 0.818610
Max value 96.8789
Min value 92.5632

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 267.944

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 1001.25
 Standard dev 0.411406
 Max value 1002.37
 Min value 1000.07

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 286.285
 Standard dev 0.581588
 Max value 287.228
 Min value 285.265

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 286.003
 Standard dev 0.519579
 Max value 286.964
 Min value 284.606

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 39.8366
 Standard dev 2.57135
 Max value 43.9413
 Min value 26.9239

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 289.854
 Standard dev 0.386685
 Max value 290.392
 Min value 288.899

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 286.182
 Standard dev 0.588125
 Max value 287.116
 Min value 285.165

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 98.3319
 Standard dev 3.77082
 Max value 108.000
 Min value 89.6006

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 36.2334
 Standard dev 0.128845
 Max value 36.4567
 Min value 36.0113

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 600
 Mean -2.49356
 Standard dev 5.05373
 Max value -2.13100
 Min value -126.059

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 2.15326
 Standard dev 13.1240
 Max value 321.835
 Min value -1.61360

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 600
 Mean -1.240985e-02
 Standard dev 13.7889
 Max value 332.054
 Min value -4.53834

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 600
 Mean -12.7412
 Standard dev 2.25365
 Max value -10.4287
 Min value -65.8284

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 598
 Mean 3.03255
 Standard dev 0.909666
 Max value 4.63389
 Min value 0.516490

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 179.670

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 600
 Mean 93.5445
 Standard dev 1.47288
 Max value 96.5925
 Min value 89.0089

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 28.9380

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 406
 Mean 1001.21
 Standard dev 0.291440
 Max value 1002.36
 Min value 1000.55

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 406
 Mean 286.788
 Standard dev 0.115593
 Max value 287.078
 Min value 286.524

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 406
 Mean 286.916
 Standard dev 0.339518
 Max value 287.394
 Min value 285.651

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 406
 Mean 33.5270
 Standard dev 2.82001
 Max value 38.4940
 Min value 22.2055

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 406
 Mean 289.050
 Standard dev 0.283423
 Max value 289.692
 Min value 288.647

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 406
 Mean 286.690
 Standard dev 0.121005
 Max value 286.947
 Min value 286.435

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 406
 Mean 99.2823
 Standard dev 2.85336
 Max value 106.141
 Min value 89.9723

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 406
 Mean 36.5051
 Standard dev 2.842689e-02
 Max value 36.5808
 Min value 36.4809

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 406
 Mean -2.65007
 Standard dev 5.99970
 Max value -2.15389
 Min value -123.223

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 406
 Mean -3.65643
 Standard dev 18.3145
 Max value -1.36498
 Min value -371.153

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 406
 Mean 0.989041
 Standard dev 19.9504
 Max value 400.508
 Min value -26.7834

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 406
 Mean -13.1895
 Standard dev 10.2317
 Max value -11.2047
 Min value -217.359

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 403
 Mean 2.97515
 Standard dev 1.00073
 Max value 7.53599
 Min value 1.51929

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 344.864

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 406
 Mean 93.5585
 Standard dev 0.610848
 Max value 95.8040
 Min value 91.7603

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 286.401

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 1001.13
 Standard dev 0.293014
 Max value 1002.61
 Min value 1000.29

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 285.978
 Standard dev 0.570306
 Max value 286.829
 Min value 284.985

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 285.987
 Standard dev 0.655739
 Max value 287.467
 Min value 284.362

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 38.9220
 Standard dev 3.34432
 Max value 44.0705
 Min value 24.7432

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 289.008
 Standard dev 0.617448
 Max value 290.198
 Min value 288.091

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 285.886
 Standard dev 0.578662
 Max value 286.739
 Min value 284.894

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 95.4844
 Standard dev 3.31591
 Max value 101.495
 Min value 79.0070

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 36.2226
 Standard dev 0.207331
 Max value 36.5784
 Min value 35.8604

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 903
 Mean -3.05226
 Standard dev 5.79568
 Max value -2.56551
 Min value -128.149

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 903
 Mean -4.24567
 Standard dev 4.74600
 Max value 115.683
 Min value -69.1531

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 903
 Mean -2.63014
 Standard dev 10.0836
 Max value 284.475
 Min value -72.0065

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 903
 Mean -12.4093
 Standard dev 4.11125
 Max value 7.78398
 Min value -133.018

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 899
 Mean 5.46228
 Standard dev 1.95010
 Max value 9.21428
 Min value 2.04885

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 31.7777

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 903
 Mean 93.9663
 Standard dev 1.27319
 Max value 97.6469
 Min value 87.0045

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 206.099

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 443
 Mean 1008.77
 Standard dev 0.276881
 Max value 1009.44
 Min value 1008.07

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 443
 Mean 287.378
 Standard dev 0.265669
 Max value 287.741
 Min value 286.815

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 443
 Mean 286.978
 Standard dev 0.418422
 Max value 287.945
 Min value 285.935

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 443
 Mean 39.9986
 Standard dev 1.06594
 Max value 42.9072
 Min value 37.6000

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 443
 Mean 289.229
 Standard dev 0.511091
 Max value 290.344
 Min value 288.455

POT TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 443
 Mean 286.663
 Standard dev 0.260664
 Max value 287.043
 Min value 286.079

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 443
 Mean 32.1115
 Standard dev 2.22485
 Max value 37.9337
 Min value 26.4109

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 443
 Mean 36.2904
 Standard dev 8.901506e-02
 Max value 36.4380
 Min value 36.1315

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 443
 Mean -1.67739
 Standard dev 7.903489e-02
 Max value -1.54925
 Min value -1.82132

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 443
 Mean -1.61838
 Standard dev 1.10198
 Max value 0.200981
 Min value -4.45443

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 443
 Mean 2.25505
 Standard dev 0.927499
 Max value 4.03119
 Min value -0.665298

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 443
 Mean -11.7774
 Standard dev 0.500210
 Max value -10.1695
 Min value -12.8356

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 443
 Mean 3.04707
 Standard dev 0.700568
 Max value 5.01145
 Min value 0.718385

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 305.666

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 443
 Mean 92.9376
 Standard dev 1.24890
 Max value 96.8005
 Min value 89.5687

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 144.322

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 1001.73
 Standard dev 0.529941
 Max value 1003.09
 Min value 999.563

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 286.781
 Standard dev 0.270445
 Max value 287.202
 Min value 286.216

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 288.347
 Standard dev 0.208381
 Max value 288.674
 Min value 287.815

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 39.5449
 Standard dev 1.41502
 Max value 42.8427
 Min value 30.0029

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 289.274
 Standard dev 0.717242
 Max value 290.417
 Min value 288.198

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 286.639
 Standard dev 0.265766
 Max value 287.048
 Min value 286.067

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 92.2358
 Standard dev 4.18469
 Max value 109.115
 Min value 79.0070

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 36.2571
 Standard dev 0.136427
 Max value 36.4967
 Min value 36.0214

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 603
 Mean -1.84525
 Standard dev 5.14053
 Max value -1.51666
 Min value -127.856

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 0.235459
 Standard dev 12.7875
 Max value 2.94006
 Min value -312.034

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 603
 Mean -1.89532
 Standard dev 15.3820
 Max value 373.047
 Min value -6.79266

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 603
 Mean -11.8456
 Standard dev 3.79054
 Max value -9.37976
 Min value -103.947

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 601
 Mean 2.94955
 Standard dev 1.47597
 Max value 6.89014
 Min value 0.788695

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 97.0817

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 603
 Mean 93.2928
 Standard dev 0.926966
 Max value 95.1254
 Min value 90.4062

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 338.898

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 1008.65
 Standard dev 0.417054
 Max value 1009.60
 Min value 1007.45

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 287.335
 Standard dev 0.202424
 Max value 287.574
 Min value 286.619

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 288.709
 Standard dev 0.210059
 Max value 289.258
 Min value 288.285

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 39.2578
 Standard dev 1.45472
 Max value 42.6698
 Min value 33.4980

CORR SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 288.822
 Standard dev 0.471351
 Max value 289.853
 Min value 288.272

POT TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 286.630
 Standard dev 0.210456
 Max value 286.883
 Min value 285.948

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 33.3434
 Standard dev 3.47625
 Max value 42.9517
 Min value 25.1099

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 36.3686
 Standard dev 9.252184e-02
 Max value 36.5235
 Min value 36.2048

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 405
 Mean -1.70885
 Standard dev 4.437180e-02
 Max value -1.64393
 Min value -1.79514

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 405
 Mean -1.80949
 Standard dev 1.22059
 Max value 0.370667
 Min value -4.67606

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 1.16433
 Standard dev 0.378967
 Max value 2.03519
 Min value -4.410553e-02

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 405
 Mean -11.5392
 Standard dev 0.625744
 Max value -10.0231
 Min value -13.8537

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 2.31353
 Standard dev 0.953488
 Max value 4.77010
 Min value 0.509954

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 327.240

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 405
 Mean 92.6947
 Standard dev 0.987256
 Max value 94.8737
 Min value 90.6537

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 159.020

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument “the fluorescence water vapour sensor”.

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm^3) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

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